

1 **Reciprocal control of Dlx and Olig homeobox transcription factors by Xist.**

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7 We describe here hierarchical positioning of two homeobox families, the Dlx and Olig families, in the
8 homeobox activation cascade resulting in transformation like that which occurs following Xist activation
9 resulting from p53 inactivation. We demonstrate that *Dlx1* and *Dlx2*, as well as *Olig1* and *Olig2* can
10 activate Xist for transformation just as Xist activation preceding transformation can result in Dlx1/2 and
11 Olig1/2 induction. The data further position Dlx1/2 and Olig1/2 proximal to initiation of transformation
12 induction, adjacent to, resulting from and generally following Xist non-coding RNA activation de novo or as
13 a result of inactivation of p53 or Rb1.
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